

TRANSLATING ENGLISH WORDS AND TEXTS OUT OF CONTEXT

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Abstract: *The article provides information on translation in English based on the context.*

Key words: *transcription, borrowed words, pronunciation, etymology, lexicology, linguistic unit of language.*

Quality and good translation from a foreign language is a real art. Therefore, not everyone can cope with its implementation. When implementing an English-Russian online translation service, it is a very necessary process, you need to take into account the smallest, sometimes even completely invisible details. For example, the specifics of translation for technical texts are very different compared to the translation of conversational speech of several interlocutors. We help you overcome this difficult task, so you can significantly save your personal time to do something more interesting.[1] The choice of meaning of words and phrases is influenced by:

- 1) Context.
- 2) metaphors, idioms.
- 3) ambiguity.

Context is the environment of the translated word or phrase. For example: Einstein's theory - Einstein's theory, Christ's theory - Christ's teaching. One word is translated differently in different environments.

Metaphor and idioms. Figurative words and phrases are translated equivalently - you need to look up the whole phrase in dictionaries or try to understand the figurative meaning that the author introduced into it. For example: I will move heaven and earth to achieve my goal - I will move mountains for my goal... See: in the original there are no contextualized words at all, but we see the sentence - "I will move heaven and earth to achieve my goal." - doesn't sound very Russian, and we're looking for something dropped from the rest of the environment - "I will move heaven and earth"... We see that this idiom, a phraseological unit, has its own dictionary equivalent "I will roll togs".[2]

Ambiguity. This is where the limitation of the topic, which we did earlier in the second step, when we created a mental image of the text, comes in handy. Based on this image, we select the most suitable one from dozens of values.[3] Translation is speech. We go a step further and match familiar words and unfamiliar word equivalents (found in current dictionaries) to sentences. At the same time, do not forget that in English there is a strict order of words, in Russian it is free. Therefore, when choosing the meaning of a word, it is necessary to look at its place in the sentence. In Russian: my mother washed the frame - my mother washed the frame - my mother washed the frame. In English: the mother washed the frame, the mother washed the frame (the meaning changes due to the change in the order of the words). Special attention is paid to verbs. Verbs in English have a number of unique features: there are phrases that are not in Russian (like get after - to pursue, take after - to be, etc.).[4]

Context (lat. "contextus" - gypsum, connection, connection) - a relatively complete part of spoken or written speech (text). Context allows you to determine the meaning of words or phrases in its context. It is related to poetics and plays an important role in determining the skill of the writer. The word is the central linguistic unit: it implements all the laws of the existence of its small language units - phonemes and morphemes, and determines its essence in advance.[5] Orthoepia (ortho... Greek. epos — speech, pronunciation) — 1) a branch of linguistics that studies the standards of literary pronunciation; 2) a system of rules ensuring the same pronunciation in accordance with the pronunciation norms of a particular national language and their observance. The uniformity of the pronunciation of spoken speech facilitates the linguistic treatment, as well as spelling. The concept of orthography is understood in two broad and narrow sense: in the broad sense - it includes the rules for using phonemes and the rules for pronouncing phoneme allophones (variants); in the narrow sense - the rules for the use of complex phonemes are introduced. Orthoepia. The reason for the difference in the scope is that some scholars include only the pronunciation of sounds in the concept of pronunciation norms, while others include the accent and sometimes the formation of variant grammatical forms. The word is the central linguistic unit: it implements all the laws of the existence of its small language units - phonemes and morphemes, and determines its essence in advance. In terms of form, all words have phonemic and morphemic forms; the second also applies to service words and participles. But phrases, that is, sentence fragments, additionally have correlative forms characteristic of narrow or broad grammatical categories: case category, in which the system of idioms is called inflection; the system of forms is the category of person called conjugation, and then - gender, number, degree, type, tense, mood, non-wide forms of voice, variously indicated in parts of speech.[6]

First, if you don't know the context in which a word is usually used, you can use it in the wrong combination with vivid imagination in the example. The meaning and use of the word is mainly determined by the context. For example, in English, "fake" means fake, "note (musical)" means note, "fake note" means fake note? To understand how to say "wrong note" in English, you need to find the English equivalent use of this musical term in a musical context. It turns out that "false note" is wrong nota, which literally means "wrong note." If we look a little more, we will find another option - wrong note, and by the way, these two terms are slightly different. But let's find out if there is a fake record or not. A fake note is a "false note".

In conclusion, it can be said that translation based on the context is mainly done with the help of pronunciation and, in turn, its transformation or transliteration methods. It depends on the skill and experience of the translator to determine which transformation method is appropriate and where. It is very important for a translator to be fluent in two languages and to be aware of all its fields. When choosing words, it is good to take into account the characteristics of the style and genre.

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ILM – FAN TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA YECHIMLAR

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE: "CONTEMPORARY
PHILOLOGICAL PARADIGM: VZAIMODEISTVIE TRADITISI I
INNOVATISI II" (Vol. 2, No. 18.03, pp. 554-560).
<https://doi.org/10.47100/nuu.v2i18.03.115>